

SPOKE 1

ACCELERATING AIRPORT DECARBONIZATION

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1. Airports as key drivers in aviation decarbonization

In recent years, the climate crisis has accelerated the need for a sustainable transition across all industrial sectors — and aviation is no exception. Traditionally seen as logistical and commercial hubs, airports are now emerging as critical players in the aviation industry's ambitious goal of achieving net-zero emissions. This is not only due to their own direct emissions, but also their ability to influence a complex ecosystem that includes airlines, passengers, service providers, logistics, and energy networks.

Decarbonizing airport operations is not merely an environmental challenge: it has become a tangible opportunity for greater efficiency. Emissions reduction is increasingly supported by mature and accessible technologies, which often translate into lower overall energy consumption, delivering both economic and operational benefits. A key role is played by the adoption of renewable energy sources — such as electricity from solar or wind power. These solutions, beyond cutting emissions, enhance operational resilience: they protect energy supply from potential market disruptions or price volatility, offering greater long-term cost stability.

In May 2019, European airports, through the **ACI EUROPE** association, publicly committed to achieving Net Zero Carbon emissions by 2050. This ambitious but essential target has led to the development of increasingly concrete and detailed action plans, aimed at identifying the most effective measures, technologies, and operational models to reach this goal. According to ACI EUROPE's guidelines, there are five key steps that help build an effective and scalable roadmap, adaptable to the specific characteristics of each airport:

1. Emissions measurement

To effectively tackle decarbonization, airports must first accurately measure their carbon footprint. The globally recognized *Greenhouse Gas (GHG)* Protocol is the standard used for this purpose. It categorizes emissions into three main scopes:

- **Scope 1:** direct emissions, such as fuel used in airport vehicles;
- **Scope 2:** indirect emissions from purchased energy (e.g., electricity used for terminals and facilities);
- **Scope 3:** indirect upstream and downstream emissions from third parties (e.g., airlines, passengers, suppliers)

Measuring carbon emissions requires thorough data collection from operations and the application of emission factors to convert this data into CO₂ equivalents. High-quality data is essential — the more detailed the measurement, the easier it becomes to identify sources, define effective actions, and prioritize interventions.

2. From measurement to identification

The next step is to identify emissions reduction measures that are effective, feasible, and scalable — both technically and economically. These can generally be addressed through two main approaches:

- Contractual solutions, such as certified energy supply agreements;
- On-site technical solutions, such as installing photovoltaic panels, heat pumps, or electric ground service equipment.

Since many of these measures may affect employees, users, or local communities, it is crucial to involve stakeholders from the beginning. Only through internal analysis and stakeholder engagement can a comprehensive list of potential actions be drafted. Naturally, not every identified action will be immediately applicable. A technical and strategic assessment is therefore necessary — mapping the proposed actions against the emissions identified in step one, and evaluating them based on factors such as relevance to the airport's context, technological maturity, logistical and operational feasibility, and implementation costs.

3. Defining the pathway to NetZero

Once possible actions are identified, the next step is to evaluate and structure coherent pathways to achieve Net Zero Carbon. This means developing alternative scenarios, each built around different combinations of actions, timelines, and investments. These scenarios are shaped by various factors, such as: impact and feasibility for the airport, level of required Investment, applicable regulatory frameworks. Each scenario represents a specific pathway, made up of concrete actions, milestones, and expected outcomes. After analyzing the options, the airport can select a preferred path, which becomes its official route to Net Zero. This pathway must be systemic and shared — a credible target can only be achieved if the entire organization is aligned on how to reach it.

4. Defining the roadmap

The final planning step is the creation of a roadmap — a strategic document that structures all previous decisions. It must be concrete, trackable, shareable, and communicable.

An effective roadmap is built on:

- Strong commitment from the entire organization, especially senior leadership;
- A clearly defined Net Zero Carbon target;
- Short-term actions ready for implementation, and medium-to-long-term actions under development;
- A regular monitoring and reporting mechanism to track progress and update the plan as needed.

5. Deliver

With the roadmap in place, the focus shifts to implementation. Feasibility studies and project designs must be developed for each identified measure to ensure effective and goal-aligned execution.

At the same time, periodic reviews — ideally on an annual basis — will help monitor the actual impact of adopted actions, track the airport's evolving carbon footprint, and quickly identify any adjustments that may be needed.

This whitepaper aims to explore the strategies airports are adopting to meet the decarbonization challenge — transforming what was once a regulatory burden into a unique opportunity to reinvent themselves as sustainable and resilient hubs.

2. How airports are transforming Net-Zero 2050 targets into opportunities to reinvent themselves and tackle carbon emissions

Regardless of their size or location, many airports around the world are adopting integrated decarbonization roadmaps that address short-, medium-, and long-term targets.

Airports, which represent one segment of the aviation sector, are responsible for approximately 15% of the industry's global emissions and play a crucial role in achieving sustainability goals. There are three key areas on which they can focus.

First, airports can begin by decarbonizing *Scope 1* emissions linked to their daily operations, as well as *Scope 2* emissions, which derive from the energy and fuel they consume. Second, they can tackle *Scope 3* emissions by promoting decarbonization among their suppliers, as well as among the airlines and service providers that use their facilities. Finally, airports should prepare for future green technologies, such as *Sustainable Aviation Fuels (SAF)* and hydrogen, by developing the necessary infrastructure to support and scale up these solutions.

While an airport must address its *Scope 1* and *2* emissions (which account for only about 3% of total emissions), the bulk of its indirect carbon footprint—and its contribution to the overall decarbonization of aviation—lies within *Scope 3*.

Before delving into a more detailed analysis, the following chart outlines the two main decarbonization options for advancing the commitment to Net-Zero aviation by 2050: fuel efficiency gains and Sustainable Aviation Fuels (SAF). This represents a decarbonization roadmap, emphasizing the combined importance of these two strategies—alongside progress in propulsion technologies and CO₂ removal—in order to meet climate goals.

The charts below depict two different scenarios for achieving this objective (between 2022 and 2050), showing the annual reduction in *GHG* emissions:

- The first illustrates the amount of *GHG* emissions expected to be avoided or reduced through the implementation of the specified solutions. Following this pathway, cumulative emissions reductions are projected to range between 21 and 22 Gt CO₂e, compared to the alternative scenario;
- The second chart represents the "Business-as-Usual" scenario, in which no significant action is taken to reduce aviation-related emissions. In this case, cumulative *GHG* emissions would amount to 47 Gt CO₂e.

Comparing these two potential pathways, it is clear that implementing these solutions would result in a net reduction of approximately 25–26 Gt CO₂e relative to the "Business-as-Usual" scenario.

Percent of cumulative GHG reduction, between 2022 and 2050:

Source: Mission Possible Partnership

2.1. Type of emissions

In the short term, the focus is on direct and indirect emissions under the airport's control:

❖ Scope 1

These are greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions that originate from sources owned or directly controlled by the airport. They are the emissions over which the airport has the most direct operational control.

Examples of direct emissions include:

- Fuel combustion in airport-owned vehicles and equipment (e.g., service vehicles, baggage transporters, fire trucks, internal shuttle buses);
- Combustion of fossil fuels (natural gas, diesel, etc.) in boilers or furnaces used for heating, electricity, or steam generation within airport buildings;
- Fugitive emissions from air conditioning or refrigeration systems;
- Emissions from specific industrial processes, if present within the airport premises (e.g., small power plants owned by the airport).

❖ **Scope 2**

These are *GHG* emissions from the generation of purchased energy (electricity, heat, steam, cooling) that is consumed by the airport. While the airport does not produce these emissions directly, it is responsible for their use.

Examples of indirect emissions from purchased energy include:

- Emissions resulting from electricity used for lighting, heating, and cooling of terminal buildings, offices, control towers, and other airport infrastructure;
- Emissions associated with purchasing heat or steam from an external source.

❖ **Scope 3**

These include all other indirect *GHG* emissions that occur within the airport's value chain, both upstream (related to suppliers) and downstream (related to customers), which are not included in *Scope 2*. These emissions are the most complex to monitor and manage but often represent the largest share of an airport's total carbon footprint.

Examples of other indirect emissions include:

- *LTO Cycle – Landing and Take-Off*: covers emissions from aircraft during taxiing, take-off, climb, approach, and landing. While airlines are responsible for these emissions, airports can influence them through traffic management strategies and infrastructure (e.g., efficient taxiing systems, use of *Fixed Electrical Ground Power (FEGP)* and *Pre-Conditioned Air (PCA)* instead of aircraft Auxiliary Power Units);
- Emissions generated by private vehicles, taxis, buses, and trains used by passengers and airport staff;
- Emissions related to the production of materials and execution of construction or maintenance works at the airport;
- Emissions from waste treatment and disposal generated by airport operations and commercial activities;
- Emissions produced by airlines, ground handlers, shops, restaurants, and other entities operating within the airport perimeter but not owned or controlled by the airport operator.

Understanding and quantifying the emissions produced within each Scope is crucial for several reasons. First and foremost, it allows airports to identify the main sources of emissions: knowing where most emissions originate helps to focus efforts where they are most effective, enabling the definition of targeted reduction goals. It also supports the development of appropriate strategies: investments in energy efficiency, renewable energy, and fleet electrification for *Scope 1* and *Scope 2*; and collaboration with airlines, suppliers, passengers, and local authorities to promote more sustainable solutions for *Scope 3*.

Everything outlined so far makes it clear that airport decarbonization is a complex challenge that requires a collaborative approach and the commitment of all stakeholders across the aviation value chain.

2.2. Scope 1 & Scope 2 deep-dive

Therefore, in the short term, it is essential for airports to analyze their current carbon footprint in order to define a decarbonization strategy based on scientific criteria. This involves identifying immediate actions aimed at reducing both direct and indirect emissions under their control, which currently account for approximately 3% of total emissions associated with the airport sector.

By acting in these two areas, airports can also help promote the large-scale adoption and distribution of Sustainable Aviation Fuels (SAF). These fuels will play an increasingly important role in reducing *Scope 3* emissions, at least until zero-emission propulsion technologies are fully developed and widely available.

Airports Going Electric – United Arab Emirates; Europe

Several leading airports are embracing the electrification of their operations as an innovative strategy to reduce carbon emissions. Here are some notable examples of this global transition.

Dubai International Airport's Terminal 2 has made a significant leap by installing the region's largest solar energy system. It consists of 15,000 photovoltaic panels, covering an area equivalent to about three football fields. Currently, this solar plant supplies 29% of the terminal's electricity needs, with ambitious plans for further expansion.

Rome-Fiumicino Airport is also implementing a comprehensive electrification strategy, including the construction of large-scale solar plants capable of generating 60 megawatts of clean energy. This not only significantly cuts the airport's carbon footprint but also sets a high benchmark for sustainable airport practices.

Electrification goes beyond buildings—it also encompasses ground operations and end-user services, both of which are critical to the daily functioning of an airport.

Sofia Airport is transitioning its ground support vehicle fleet to electric mobility. The goal is to replace all vehicles with zero-climate-impact alternatives. So far, the airport has integrated 34 electric or hybrid vehicles and is installing 22 charging stations to support this shift, while also upgrading the grid infrastructure needed for electric vehicles.

These efforts serve as a replicable model for airports worldwide, demonstrating the feasibility and benefits of comprehensive decarbonization strategies in the aviation sector. They also highlight the growing electricity demands at airports—and the opportunity to generate this energy on-site when land or rooftop space is available.

2.3. Scope 3 deep-dive

Looking to the long term, the challenge intensifies as airports commit to addressing Scope 3 emissions.

Alternative propulsion technologies—such as hybrid-electric, fully electric, and hydrogen-powered aircraft—are expected to contribute significantly to reducing greenhouse gas emissions, with a potential impact of up to 15% by 2050. Airports can already begin preparing the infrastructure and systems needed to accommodate these emerging solutions.

Hydrogen's Contribution to Aviation Sustainability

Countries with abundant natural resources and high potential for green hydrogen production could become strategic hubs for a new aviation supply chain based on this energy carrier. However, it is essential that airports conduct feasibility studies to assess key aspects such as design, logistics, infrastructure, and refueling methods needed to build a functional and sustainable regional hydrogen aviation ecosystem.

Airports around the world are currently exploring the economic and operational implications of developing hydrogen infrastructure, also evaluating the potential business opportunities it may offer.

In recent years, numerous partnerships have emerged between airports, airlines, and aircraft manufacturers—such as the recent agreement between **Airbus** and **Toronto Pearson International Airport**—with the goal of assessing the real-world feasibility of hydrogen infrastructure.

In May 2024, Airbus signed an agreement with Toronto Pearson International Airport, along with Montréal and Vancouver airports, to launch feasibility studies on integrating hydrogen into airport operations. The goal is to evaluate how to prepare airport infrastructure to accommodate future hydrogen-powered aircraft, in view of the launch of Airbus's first zero-emission aircraft expected by 2035.

The initiative involves analyzing the technical and logistical requirements for producing, storing, and distributing hydrogen, as well as the development of operational standards and procedures. For Toronto Pearson—one of North America's major aviation hubs—this agreement represents a tangible step toward decarbonizing the sector and reinforces its position among the global leaders in sustainable airport innovation.

The agreement is part of Airbus's global "Hydrogen Hubs at Airports" program, which aims to build an international network of airports ready to support hydrogen aviation. Through collaboration with industrial and institutional stakeholders, Toronto Pearson aims to lead the transition to a zero-emissions future.

Therefore, in order to develop effective decarbonization strategies, it is essential to understand the composition of an airport's carbon footprint. While airports have direct control over their own operational emissions (*Scope 1* and *2*), the main challenge lies in managing the indirect emissions generated by related activities.

The chart below, based on in-depth analyses by Roland Berger for advanced airports, provides a detailed breakdown of an airport's emissions by source. It clearly shows that *Scope 3* emissions represent the overwhelming majority of the total footprint, highlighting the importance of a collaborative and holistic approach to achieving Net Zero targets.

As previously mentioned, direct airport emissions account for a relatively small share of the total footprint (~3%); emissions from purchased and consumed energy represent only about 1%. The most striking figure is that over 90% of an airport's carbon footprint comes from *Scope 3* emissions. This means that an

airport's decarbonization efforts must focus much more on collaborating with airlines, suppliers, passengers, and other stakeholders, rather than solely on its own direct operations.

N.B. The 3% Scope 1 and 1% Scope 2 allocation applies to environmentally "mature" airports. Less advanced airports may have higher Scope 1 and 2 allocations (8-15%).

Source: Roland Berger

Aircraft operations (taxiing, take-off, climb, approach, APU use) represent the largest share of total emissions. This highlights the importance of Sustainable Aviation Fuels (SAF) and innovative propulsion technologies (as previously discussed) in reducing the carbon footprint. Passenger and employee transportation is another major contributor, emphasizing the need for public transport and sustainable mobility solutions to and from the airport.

Thus, as illustrated so far, *Scope 3* emissions constitute the largest part of an airport's carbon footprint, representing the most significant challenge on the path to decarbonization. These emissions, which are not directly controlled by the airport operator, require a targeted and collaborative approach. The following chart presents a "mitigation toolbox", outlining concrete strategies to address the five main *Scope 3* contributors.

	STANDING & TAXIING	TAKE-OFF & CLIMB	APPROACH	PASSENGER & EMPLOYEE TRANSPORT	CONSTRUCTION
MAIN MITIGATION STRATEGIES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electric towing of aircraft Provision of Ground Power Units (GPU as a service) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduction of ground queuing times 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementation of continuous descent procedures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promotion of green public transport 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of green construction materials
POSSIBLE IMPACT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Complete abatement of emissions during this phase 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Airport - dependent 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Approx. 100 kg of fuel saved per flight with continuous descent 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Airport - dependent 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Airport - dependent
ACTIONS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Purchase electric tow vehicles Implement GPU services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaboration with relevant stakeholders to optimize air traffic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaboration with relevant stakeholders to optimize air traffic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implement incentive policies Engage in lobbying efforts involve passengers and employees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define carbon pricing Integrate sustainability into airport master plans Collaborate with green material suppliers
STAKEHOLDERSE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Airlines Ground handling services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Airlines, Air Navigation Service Providers (ANSPs), ATC technology developers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Airlines, Air Navigation Service Providers (ANSPs), ATC technology developers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local governments & transport companies, passengers, employees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Constructors, investors, local government, green material suppliers
EXAMPLES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deployment of "taxibots" at Delhi Airport Air India reporting CO2 savings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Airports like Schiphol, Geneva, or Heathrow offering waivers on landing charges for efficient flights 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Airports like Schiphol, Geneva, or Heathrow offering waivers on landing charges for efficient flights 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Shuttle service for Beauvais Airport in France covering about 50% of passenger traffic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of 50% recycled steel in the T2 extension at Oslo Airport

Source: ICAO, NLR, Roland Berger

The diagram details, for each main source of Scope 3 emissions (illustrated in the previous chart), the most effective mitigation levers. For each lever, it highlights the key strategies or technologies to reduce emissions, the specific actions that can be undertaken, the expected potential impact, and the key stakeholders that need to be involved. Concrete examples of implementation are also provided, demonstrating the feasibility of these measures. From reducing taxiing times through electric towing to adopting green materials for infrastructure, the diagram emphasizes the need for coordinated action between the airport and all actors in its value chain to achieve significant decarbonization goals.

Ultimately, the future of net-zero aviation will be shaped by a synergistic combination of technological innovation, operational efficiency, investments in sustainable fuels and infrastructure, and a collective commitment from all stakeholders in the sector. Only through this shared vision and joint actions will it be possible to make aviation a pillar of truly sustainable mobility.

3. Looking beyond decarbonization: prioritizing customer experience

Strategic and forward-looking solutions designed to address current challenges can generate lasting benefits that go far beyond simply reducing emissions. For example, reducing passenger transport emissions is not enough unless it is accompanied by an improvement in the user experience of public transport, making sustainable alternatives more attractive to travelers.

Initiatives such as off-airport check-in or separate baggage transport are concrete examples of interventions that enhance the overall service. Several airport infrastructures have already adopted these solutions, often in collaboration with external companies like *Airportr* and *Alltheway*.

These examples clearly demonstrate the great potential of decisive and timely action to reduce CO₂ emissions in airport areas. At the same time, however, they highlight the importance of constructive dialogue with all stakeholders involved, particularly airlines and aviation service providers. Roland Berger suggests that airport managing companies take the initiative by creating local working groups dedicated to decarbonization, involving all relevant actors at each individual airport.

This approach allows airports not only to actively lead the path towards sustainability but also to facilitate the coordination of complex actions capable of effectively reducing the indirect *Scope 3* emissions generated by airport activities.

4. Conclusions

The decarbonization of airports represents one of the most complex yet strategic challenges for the future of aviation. In an increasingly sustainability-driven global context, airports can no longer be mere logistical hubs: they must transform into active platforms for environmental innovation and the ecological transition of the aviation sector.

As highlighted, the path toward Net Zero Carbon is not linear but requires a systemic and adaptable approach, structured in well-defined phases: from accurate measurement of the carbon footprint to the identification of reduction measures, from building strategic scenarios to defining operational roadmaps, up to concrete implementation and continuous monitoring of results.

While airports have limited direct control (*Scope 1* and *2* account for only a small portion of total emissions), their capacity to influence indirectly (*Scope 3*) is enormous. For this reason, the environmental challenge is also a relational one: no airport can achieve ambitious climate goals without effective collaboration with airlines, suppliers, public stakeholders, and passengers.

At the same time, decarbonization should not be viewed merely as a regulatory obligation but as an opportunity for industrial transformation, competitive positioning, and long-term resilience. Technologies available today — from sustainable fuels to infrastructure electrification, from the use of renewable energy to operational optimization — not only allow emissions reductions but also improve efficiency, safety, and the quality of airport services.

Finally, regulatory support and the definition of shared technical standards — for example, for hydrogen refueling — will be essential to enable an effective transition toward a future characterized by multiple fuel sources.

In conclusion, the transition to climate-neutral airports represents a strategic lever to rethink the entire aviation ecosystem. Airports that seize this opportunity will not only make a decisive contribution to the fight against climate change but will also establish themselves as central players in a new model of mobility that is more sustainable, smart, and inclusive.

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